

Managing risk and building trustworthy AI solutions: Lessons from FTI Consulting

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21 May 2025

As generative AI (“GenAI”) systems become more sophisticated, more reliable and more accessible, there is an increasing imperative for organisations to make the most of this technology. [FTI Consulting](#), a global firm providing expertise for organisations facing crises and transformation, is no exception. With more than 8,000 employees located in 34 countries, FTI Consulting helps its clients manage change, mitigate risk and resolve disputes in areas ranging from financial, legal and regulatory to reputational and operational.

FTI Consulting’s Data & Analytics team is a hub of innovation, a leading component of the company’s drive towards AI adoption – for the benefit of its staff and its clients. Team members have been part of the 2024 cohort of *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub, acting as Experts in Residence (“EiRs”) on behalf of the company and exploring how issues of ethics and responsibility are necessary components of technological advancement.

“We deploy AI-focused solutions as internal tools but also in our projects with external clients,” says Dr Dimitris Korres, Managing Director and Global Principal Data Scientist at FTI Consulting. “That covers a wide range of techniques and applications, from traditional machine learning to the more recent GenAI boom.”

Using AI (Responsibly) to Improve Internal Processes

Over the past few years, the team has built a suite of internal AI tools, optimising FTI Consulting’s operations and enhancing efficiency for colleagues. These tools include:

- **FTI Expert:** GenAI-driven platform to supercharge expert identification and business development across FTI Consulting. By leveraging FTI bios, thought leadership, and other available internal data sources, FTI Expert enhances and streamlines the search for expertise.
- **FTI IntelliSearch:** An AI-driven knowledge management solution designed to optimise intellectual resources – including past project outputs, business development materials, and intellectual capital – FTI IntelliSearch streamlines business development and the exploratory stages of client engagements.

- **FTI Creator:** An AI-driven solution to expedite the generation of high-quality first drafts of pitch materials and templated content creation.
- **FTI Nomos:** An AI-driven platform to help teams navigate evolving regulatory landscapes, FTI Nomos helps automate tasks such as regulation deconstruction, the mapping of related regulations, and the development of enriched regulatory inventories, enhancing FTI's ability to conduct regulatory assessments.
- **FTI Ariadne:** A self-service RAG¹ tool that enables users to efficiently manage, process, and interact with large volumes of documents stored in SharePoint, FTI Ariadne leverages secure, best-in-class LLMs² to allow users to use natural language and prompting to identify documents and generate impactful insights more quickly.
- **FTI GPT:** Harnessing the power of advanced LLMs, FTI GPT will revolutionise ideation, research, and content creation for FTI by providing secure access to several best-in-class LLM solutions – supporting content summarisation, web search, and templated responses generation – to optimise workflows and streamline day-to-day tasks.

For FTI GPT, FTI Consulting has invested in the development of an internal tool designed to support responsible and secure use of LLMs. This internal platform provides access to a curated selection of models, with options that accommodate regional data residency requirements. By enabling users – only with the explicit approval of the client or data owner – to leverage LLMs, the tool ensures that data is handled in a controlled environment, reducing the risk of exposure or misuse while still delivering the benefits of AI-assisted workflows. When discussing the FTI GPT solution, Nathalie Baker, Managing Director and EMEA Lead Data Scientist at FTI Consulting said: “The rationale behind developing our internal solution comes from our cautious approach to handling data within AI tools. While OpenAI’s API does not use submitted data for training models, a limitation was the lack of control over the specific geographic region where the data is processed. Although this is evolving, for now, it presents a limitation for certain use cases. That said, where no sensitive data is involved, OpenAI can still be accessed through the API as part of our tool. Additionally, the platform integrates other models via Amazon Web Services (“AWS”) Bedrock, offering further flexibility and control over how and where data is processed.”

A commitment to open source underpins much of FTI Consulting’s internal AI work. Dimitris says: “We definitely see ourselves as part of the open-source community, which of course is very much represented by [The Turing Way](#). We started in data science here when there weren’t many off-the-shelf, third-party solutions, so we had to look elsewhere. This has worked well because relying on third-party vendors can result in lengthy update cycles and can create vendor lock-in, which can limit future flexibility. Open-source tools let us modify and deploy solutions quickly.” There are other benefits too, says Nathalie: “When you work too far from the raw code, you lose the intuition and understanding you get from playing with the data. In the non-explainable world of natural language processing, for example, that’s when things can start to go very wrong.”

The Internal AI tools built by the team have been extensively tested in a User Acceptance Testing framework and are in the process of gradually being introduced to FTI Consulting’s 8,000+ employees globally, in line with internal AI policies and local regulations, and together with AI-related training and awareness activities.

¹Retrieval Augmented Generation

²Large Language Models

A framework to Prevent AI Failure and ‘AI Washing’

To help the company and its clients adhere to standards and avoid costly mistakes – and to comply with emerging, consumer-focused legislation such as the [EU Artificial Intelligence Act](#) – the data science team at FTI Consulting has created an AI Assessment Framework.

Based on a series of concentric circles and developed through FTI Consulting’s experience with its own in-house tools, along with external input from experts including Professor Luciano Floridi at Yale University, the framework begins with core elements such as data quality, model accuracy and infrastructure security, as shown in Figure 1. It then moves from general principles, including transparency and sustainability through to the product’s practical risks (bias, model drift, data leakage and so on), ending with broader business implications such as regulatory compliance or reputational risk. According to Dr Claudio Calvino, Senior Managing Director and Global Head of Data Science at FTI Consulting, “Any AI system can fail. Every time a machine does something inappropriate or unintended, that’s a failure – and often it goes unnoticed. Our framework enables the developers of AI tools to identify, mitigate and prevent issues. And it needs to be flexible to account for the rapid pace of technological change.”

Figure 1: FTI AI Assessment Framework

Real-world AI failures featured in news reports provide valuable cautionary lessons and highlight the risks of poorly designed systems. Examples include an AI employment model that discriminates

against older applicants due to flawed training data³, and another model that led to the purchase of property at inflated prices, resulting in significant financial losses⁴. Another issue is ‘AI washing’, in which companies exaggerate the presence or benefits of AI technologies in their tools and products. “The AI industry is a bit of a bubble – everyone thinks they can do AI, but in practice, we see a lot of failures,” Nathalie observed. “One common pitfall is data leakage, where models are trained and tested on the same data or trained on data that doesn’t match what the model would see in real life. In both cases, it can lead to inflated claims of accuracy. Part of being a responsible developer is ensuring the model does what it says on the packet, as well as educating users on how to interpret what comes out of the model. Expectations need to be managed too because AI isn’t a cure-all.”

At FTI Consulting, error mitigation is driven by an approach that includes code reviews, training, continuous knowledge-sharing, and close collaboration across all team members, all aimed at ensuring the reliability and performance of systems. “Everyone on our team has made errors in model training – it’s unavoidable,” adds Dimitris. “But we are pretty good at keeping each other on track at FTI Consulting. One of the reasons it’s important to have a diverse team from different backgrounds is the range of perspectives people can bring to problem-solving and reviewing the work.”

While FTI Consulting’s AI Assessment Framework focuses largely on the technical aspects of AI product development, engaging with The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has allowed the team to explore the ethical side. Haneen Abdelqader, Data & Analytics Senior Consultant at FTI Consulting said: “There are lots of places to share technical best practices, but not many where the focus is on the responsible delivery of AI. I’ve particularly enjoyed the cross-sector collaboration within the Practitioners Hub, hearing about how AI ethics are being applied in sectors such as the NHS that deal with highly sensitive data, and where teams have to be incredibly careful in how they develop and deploy their AI tools.” As part of the programme, the team also led a themed session, sharing details of and learnings from their organisational framework with fellow Practitioners Hub Experts in Residents as part of its two-way approach to participation in the Hub.

Challenges and FTI Consulting’s Approach to AI Adoption

FTI Consulting recognises the multifaceted challenges inherent in the rapidly evolving AI landscape. To navigate these complexities, the FTI Consulting team has proactively established a flexible framework for AI utilisation and built a team of experienced data scientists characterised by a diverse cultural and professional background. A critical challenge, they emphasise, is managing user expectations, particularly when integrating AI into their products and services. To address this, FTI Consulting relies on robust training and governance processes to prevent overestimation of AI’s capabilities as well as on the centralisation of certain AI-related activities and development best practices. They have also invested in fostering knowledge-sharing and collaboration across their large, distributed team, especially when dealing with the complexities of the code review process.

Successful AI adoption necessitates cultural shifts, including enhanced data readiness and rigorous testing. Therefore, ensuring the review and validation of AI systems, coupled with strict regulatory compliance, notably adherence to the EU AI Act, remains a key commitment for FTI Consulting’s responsible and effective AI deployment.

³Source: [Reuters, Tutoring firm settles US agency’s first bias lawsuit involving AI software](#)

⁴Source: [CNN Business, Zillow’s home-buying debacle shows how hard it is to use AI to value real estate](#)

Next Steps: Product Rollout and Ethical Exploration

For most of FTI Consulting’s AI-based internal tools (the exception being FTI Expert, FTI GPT, and FTI Ariadne), widespread deployment within the company is still pending: as Claudio notes, “technology advances quickly, but governance and approval processes often take longer”. The products are being tested with hundreds of employees to make sure they are ready for rollout. Claudio adds: “We envisage FTI Ariadne and the internal GPT being the most popular. But a company of 8,000 people is going to mirror society in the sense that some people will be keen to adopt and use AI tools, whereas others will always be sceptical of new technologies.” He adds: “We spent 2024 using investment from within the company to develop AI-based ideas that would help us streamline our operations. This year we are focusing on transferring the IP we developed to support our clients in the market.”

The team also plans to continue the exploration of AI ethics it has enjoyed through its participation in the Practitioners Hub. “I like the idea of continuing to meet up with other people in the community to share knowledge and best practices beyond technical things like coding and algorithms,” said Nathalie. “As an additional area of collaboration, that’s really interesting to me.”

Key Takeaways

1. FTI Consulting, a global technical firm, has proactively built measures for AI risks, recognising that any AI system can fail if not responsibly managed. They employ standards and frameworks to identify and mitigate issues like data leakage and hallucinations (through methodologies like RAG frameworks).
2. To prioritise data security and compliance, FTI Consulting’s Data & Analytics team has developed secure, internal AI tools, including a tiered GPT system, providing a safe alternative to public large language models for handling sensitive data.
3. The team emphasises knowledge sharing and collaboration, valuing diverse perspectives in problem-solving and error mitigation.
4. FTI Consulting acknowledges real-world AI challenges, including ‘AI Washing’, and emphasises managing user expectations through the practical experience of data experts and rigorous validation methods.
5. Supporting open-source AI development, FTI Consulting credits it for enabling rapid deployment and fostering a deeper understanding of AI systems, facilitating continuous improvement and flexible adaptation to evolving regulatory and technical needs.

Expert in Residence Spotlight: FTI Consulting Team

Haneen Abdelqader is a Senior Consultant at FTI Consulting, based in London. Haneen has a strong background in strategy and product development for AI-driven solutions. With a unique blend of technical expertise and strategic thinking, she has a proven track record of driving AI implementation across various industries, including financial services and governmental institutions. Haneen is recognised for her academic excellence as recipient of multiple awards from top-tier academic institutions.

Ignacio Pascale is a Director and Senior Data Scientist at FTI Consulting. Ignacio's expertise covers designing and building machine learning solutions, particularly in NLP and forecasting. He

is currently technically leading development of Agentic / RAG internal applications.

Nathalie Baker is a Managing Director and Lead Data Scientist in FTI Consulting's EMEA region, specialising in building robust data solutions for clients, particularly in the litigation space. Nathalie has led projects utilising natural language processing (NLP) techniques to identify key information, and her experience spans predictive modelling, data engineering, and software development.

Dr. Dimitris Korres is FTI Consulting's Principal Data Scientist based in Boston, with over 10 years of experience in developing machine learning solutions and advanced system automation. Dimitris has led projects in the financial services, media, and e-commerce industries. His work includes developing recommendation engines, geospatial analytics, and customer value models.

Dr. Claudio Calvino is a Senior Managing Director in the Data & Analytics Team and Global Head of Data Science at FTI Consulting, based in London. He specialises in data science, econometrics, and statistical analysis, and has developed algorithms and methodologies applied to global investigations, supply chain optimisation, and fraud detection. Claudio is also an International Fellow at Yale University's Digital Ethical Center.

Highlights from *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub*

“We took part in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub to make sure that our team has a clear understanding of what’s happening outside our industry. We’re all learning – it’s a very fluid industry and environment, and our team has attracted a lot of attention since GenAI hit the mainstream – so we want to do things the right way. But we were also committed to sharing our own experiences and lessons, as well as seeking to learn from others. It’s been a very interesting and valuable exercise.”

Acknowledgements

This case study is published under [The Turing Way Practitioners Hub 2024-25 Cohort](#) - case study series. The Practitioners Hub is [The Turing Way](#) project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2024, The Turing Way team welcomed **FTI Consulting** team members as Experts in Residence to represent interests and opportunities to discuss, adopt and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI in **FTI Consulting** and related sectors. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

This work is supported by [Innovate UK BridgeAI](#). The Practitioners Hub has also received funding and support from the Ecosystem Leadership Award under the EPSRC Grant EP/X03870X/1 & [The Alan Turing Institute](#).

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2024-25 Cohort was co-delivered by Dr **Malvika Sharan**, Senior Researcher - Open Research and **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher - Open Source Practices. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: turing-way@turing.ac.uk.

Cite this publication:

Abdelqader, H., Baker, N., Calvino, C., Korres, D., Pascale, I., Gillespie, S., Sharan, M. (2025). Managing risk and building trustworthy AI solutions: Lessons from FTI Consulting. Shared under CC-BY 4.0 International License. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15480555>, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15480555.